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**“GEOGRAFIK TADQIQOTLAR: INNOVATSION G‘OYALAR
VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI”**

XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY VA O‘RTA MAXSUS TA‘LIM
VAZIRLIGI
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**GEOGRAFIK TADQIQOTLAR:
INNOVATSION G‘OYALAR VA RIVOJLANISH
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WHO OR WHAT IS THE MAIN CULPRIT OF GLOBAL WARMING?

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Annotation. This article highlights that the main causes of global warming are related to the production of military weapons. It has also been analyzed geographically and geopolitically that changes for carbon dioxide in the atmosphere under the influence of anthropogenic factors are one of the important factors shaping the “greenhouse effect”.

Keywords: carbon dioxide, global warming, arms production, “greenhouse effect”, pollution.

INTRODUCTION. Observing the actions of young people on the problem of climate warming and environmental activists, the reactions of the rulers of states to them and the inconclusive conclusion of the Climate Summit, I decided to share my thoughts on this topical issue.

THE MAIN PART. At the climate summit, the main cause of warming is almost unanimously recognized as an increase in the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere. Measures have been outlined to reduce CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere through a complete transition to green energy. However, is this feasible with world coal consumption in the last decade according to the “WP Statistical Review of World Energy”¹, does not fall below 7.4 billion tons/year²; average for 2016-2020, oil consumption was 4.7 billion tons/year, gas – 4 092.9 billion cubic meters per year [1]?

In the European Union (EU), it is believed that 33 % of fuel and energy resources are spent on transport, 26 % – on industry, 25% – on domestic needs [2]. However, this ratio is questionable. For example, in 2018, global iron smelting amounted to 1.2 billion tons [3], steel – 1.8 billion tons [4], only 3 billion tons. It is known that to obtain a ton of pig iron, 1.5 - 2.0 tons of iron ore, 1.0 - 1.2 tons of coking coal and only 4-5 tons of raw materials and fuel are consumed. They point to the consumption of most of the fuel and energy resources only for the smelting of iron and steel – raw materials

¹ June, Year 2018

² until 2000 it did not exceed 4 billion tons/year

for ferrous metallurgy, most of which is spent on the production of weapons, and it has large volumes that are difficult to control due to high profitability and support at the state level. Therefore, at present, more than 50 countries produce weapons and their geography is increasingly expanding. This is clearly evidenced by the data on arms exports; in 2020, it amounted to more than 22.8 billion US dollars. The main arms exporters are the USA (\$9.37 billion), Russia (\$3.2 billion), France (\$1.99 billion), Germany (\$1.23 billion), Spain (\$1.2 billion) and others. Over the past 20 years, arms exports have been carried out for more than \$520 billion [5]. Nevertheless, it is very difficult to establish how much weapons were produced for themselves. As of 2020, the countries of the world had 98 396 tanks, 34 606 combat aircraft, 12 653 combat helicopters, more than a thousand different warships, 166 nuclear and 346 non-nuclear submarines, about 40 aircraft carriers, 13 810 nuclear warheads requiring constant care and enormous costs [6], exactly, fuels. If we add here the expenditure of fuel and lubricants for endless military exercises, then we can imagine the share of the expenditure of fuel and energy resources for military purposes. All this cannot but affect the balance of CO₂ in the atmosphere. In addition, all metallurgical stages are sources of pollution with dust, carbon oxides and sulfur [7].

It is known that warming air leads to an increase in its moisture capacity. And this enhances circulation processes, increases precipitation, the frequency of typhoons, thunderstorms, forest fires, floods over large areas, etc., which is currently observed almost everywhere on the globe, leading to great destruction and even human casualties, often destroying buildings and even populated areas. This has become more frequent in the EU and the US. The high profitability of the arms trade is of great importance here. Moreover, arms manufacturers need constant wars. For this, various reasons are found, often far-fetched. For the Iraq war, carried out by George Bush for a far-fetched reason, Obama asked for forgiveness from the world community. Poison peoples, tribes on each other. These wars have brought Iraq, Libya, Afghanistan, etc. to what.

Moreover, in these wars, it is not the fighting soldiers who die, but civilians. According to statistics, in the First World War, the number of civilians killed was only 5 %, in the second it reached 48 %, and at present almost all the victims of the war – 90% – are civilians, and most of them are women, old people and children.

Until now, it is not known who financed and is financing ISIS and others in various countries, who is arming them, who is financing terrorists? Who, under the guise of democratization, creates armed opposition? There is only one answer; they are created under pressure from manufacturers and arms dealers. However, the production of weapons is mainly carried out by state-owned enterprises. This is confirmed by the refusal of former US President Donald Trump to condemn the murder of Saudi journalist Jamal Khashoggi by the organizers of this murder; as Trump himself admitted, he was afraid of losing a \$100 billion arms deal to the Saudis.

At present, the production of weapons is carried out in many countries. However, the main producers are the USA, the EU, Russia, China and other developed countries. Due to the production of weapons in huge volumes, metallurgy and industries using its products create about 80% of world GDP. They are the main consumers of energy resources and, accordingly, the main supplier of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere and the main culprit of modern warming and its consequences in the form of flooding and destruction of settlements, death of people, especially in the USA, EU, Russia, and China.

CONCLUSION. This leads to the conclusion that it is necessary to sharply reduce the cost of fuel and energy resources for the production of weapons, transporting them around the world to conduct endless military exercises and wars, which is the main reason for the increase in the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere.

Used literatures

1. OPEC Annual Statistical Bulletin, 2020. <https://www.rogtecmagazine.com/2020-opec-annual-statistical-bulletin/>
2. *Пронин Е.Н.* Парадоксы борьбы за чистый воздух. www.gazpronin.ru. 15.06.2014. <https://gazpronin.ru/GazPronin2013.shtml>
3. Новости рынка черных металлов. www.metalbulletin.ru. 08.02.2019. <https://www.metalbulletin.ru/news/black>
4. Мировое производство стали. www.metallurgprom.org. 25.01.2019. <https://metallurgprom.org/main/19-mirovoe-proizvodstvo-syroj-stali-v-2018-godu-uvelichilos-na-46.html>
5. Крупнейшие в мире экспортеры оружия и военной техники. www.svspb.net. <https://svspb.net/sverige/eksport-vooruzhenija.php#>.
Market share of the leading exporters of major weapons between 2016 and 2020, by country. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/267131/market-share-of-the-leading-exporters-of-conventional-weapons/>
6. Список всех стран по военной мощи 2020. www.gidnenuzen.ru. 12.05.2021. <https://gidnenuzen.ru/spisok-vseh-stran-po-voennoy-moschi-2020/>
7. Большина Н.П. Экология металлургического производства. Новотроицк: НФ НИТУ «МИСиС», 2012. – С. 155.